

METHOD OF DEVELOPING WRESTLERS' SPEED-POWER QUALITIES THROUGH ACTION GAMES

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Abstract: This article discusses modern pedagogical methods for the effective use of movement games in developing the speed and strength qualities of wrestlers.

Keywords: wrestler, speed, strength, training planning, athlete's cognitive activity, pedagogical assessment.

Annotatsiya: данной статье рассматриваются современные педагогические методы эффективного использования игр-действий в развитии быстро-силовых качеств борцов.

Ключевые слова: борец, ловкость, сила, планирование тренировки, познавательная деятельность спортсмена, педагогическая оценка.

Introduction Thanks to the independence of our republic and the tireless efforts of kurash officials, kurash has developed as a new sport in the world. According to the Resolution No. PQ-4881 dated 04.11.2020 "On measures to develop the national sport of kurash and further increase its international prestige", it was adopted in order to further develop and popularize kurash among young people, strengthen the feelings of national pride and patriotism in the growing generation, as well as promote a healthy lifestyle in society and ensure high results in world sports arenas. This resolution serves as the basis for further development and popularity of our national sport of kurash in our country and in the world. As a result of the direct support of our state and the international kurash association, the international sport "Kurash" is widely recognized in the world. Terms such as "Kurash", "halol", "ta'zim", "tokhta", "yonbosh" have firmly taken their place among international sports words and phrases. Kurash has long been a symbol of nobility, courage and honesty, a part of the national and cultural heritage of our people, which has a history of several thousand years, and is an invaluable asset.

In the literature of our country and foreign scientists, work has been carried out on the problems of this topic. Among them, the following literature can be mentioned. N.A. Tastanov, F.A. Kerimov, Z.A. Bakiyev, Sh.A. Abdullayev. Foreign scientists such as V.M. Zasiorsky, A.D. Novikov, L.P. Matveyev, V.N. Platonov, N.G. Ozolin, I.I. Alikhanov, P.F. Matrushak have conducted a number of studies on the development of wrestlers and expressed their ideas and opinions in special literature.

Many scientists and experienced coaches in this field emphasize that the use of movement games in the development of the physical qualities of young wrestlers is highly effective, and movement games, including national folk games, are one of the main tools in developing their physical qualities. When analyzing the literature listed above and other sources, attention was paid to the methods and techniques of using movement games, among other tools, in the development of the physical qualities of wrestlers, but very little information was provided on the classification of games in the use of movement games in the development of the physical abilities of young wrestlers. In our opinion, therefore, today it is necessary to pay attention to the need to improve the process of using movement games in the development of the physical qualities of young wrestlers. Today, one of the urgent tasks is to develop a new technology for using movement games in the development of the physical qualities of young wrestlers, to classify the movement games used.

During the pedagogical experiment, we included movement games in the training curriculum in order to determine the effectiveness of movement games in developing the physical qualities of young wrestlers in the experimental group and develop the necessary recommendations. In this case, we selected movement games based on the characteristics of the methods and techniques for developing physical qualities. We conducted the training based on the following methodology:

1. In the preparatory part of each training session, relay action games were widely used. The goal was to warm up the wrestlers' bodies and the entire muscular system and prepare their bodies for the main part.
2. Action games were determined based on the task of the training session.
3. Action games were organized in a competitive manner. The goal was to increase the wrestlers' interest in training.

4. In the final part of the training, games that develop attention were used.

5. We paid special attention to the development of each physical quality in action games and, having planned them in advance, set separate tasks for each game.

In conclusion, the analysis of special scientific and methodological literature can serve as a basis for recognizing that the targeted use of movement games in the training process of young wrestlers makes it possible to solve the problem of developing their physical qualities, and in order to introduce movement games into the training process in the movement preparation of young wrestlers, it is necessary to determine the norms of intensity and volume of movement games and develop a methodology for their application. Movement games serve to increase the interest and desire of young wrestlers to training. We believe that the methods and tools used by us will greatly help in educating the physical qualities of young wrestlers and achieving high results in sports.

Used literature

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